

DYNAMO-bio

Deliverable: D6.1 Data Management Plan

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Project Deliverable Information Sheet

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Introduction

This document is Deliverable 6.1 and concerns the Data Management Plan (DMP) for the DYNAMO-bio project. The purpose of this deliverable is to support the data management life cycle for all data that will be collected, processed or generated by the project. It provides a description of the data types the project will generate and how the data will be collected and stored and made available for validation, exploitation and re-use by others.

The information in this DMP will be updated during the course of the project.

Data summary

DYNAMO-bio is mainly a methodological and computational project. It will develop and adapt computational methods, implement them in software tools, and illustrate their usefulness and performance by applying them to selected biomedical and biotechnological applications.

Data origins and data reuse

DYNAMO-bio will generate models and simulated data, mainly consisting of time series of the models' state variables. Such time series data will be generated by integrating the equations of dynamic models with numerical solvers in MATLAB, and possibly in other similar computational environments (e.g. Python, Julia, C, F90).

When needed, additional experimental or pseudo-experimental data (i.e., synthetically generated through simulations) will be retrieved from public repositories or publications. Experimental data will be of the same type and will be treated in the same manner as the simulated data.

Furthermore, we may obtain experimental data from the following external collaborators:

- Microbial consortia data (e.g. of bacteria *E. coli* and *B. subtilis*, and the yeast *S. cerevisiae*) from our external collaborator Hidde de Jong (INRIA).
- Cell signalling data from our collaborators Julio Saez-Rodríguez (Heidelberg) and Neda Bagheri (Washington).

Data types and formats

- Graphics: .jpeg, .pdf, .png, .eps
- Tables: .xlsx

- Text: .docx, .pdf, .txt
- MATLAB data files: .mat

DYNAMO-bio will also generate software implementing the new methods, which will be open source and shared in public repositories (Github or Gitlab, with snapshots in Zenodo):

- MATLAB source code: .m
- Other source code: Python notebooks, Julia scripts, C and F90 code.

Expected size of data

The expected size of the data will be in the order of gigabytes (< 10 GB), with individual data files of < 10 MB.

Usefulness of data

We expect that the project data may be of interest for the communities doing research in biological modelling, biomedical engineering, computational biology and biotechnology, and systems and control theory.

FAIR data

All the collected data and research outputs will comply with the FAIR principle (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable) and will be managed according to the DMP, addressing data organisation and curation, and making adequate provisions for its access, preservation, sharing, and eventual deletion, both during and after the project implementation.

Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

All datasets will have a DOI (digital object identifier), and will be referenced by it in the publications. We will use version control to manage and track the evolution of our software, data, and models.

Making data accessible

Data will be stored in public repositories:

- Github (<https://github.com/afvillaverde>) for software, and specifically the coordinator's page (<https://github.com/afvillaverde>).
- Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/>) for data and code snapshots, and specifically CITMAga's Zenodo community (<https://zenodo.org/communities/citmaga/about>)

Furthermore, data will be included as supplementary information with the corresponding publications.

Making data interoperable

In the community of dynamic biological modelling, no universally accepted set of standards exists. When possible, and for those purposes for which it may be convenient, we will attempt to use the formats of the COmputational Modeling in Biology NEtwork (COMBINE, <https://co.mbine.org/>).

Increase data reuse

DYNAMO-bio adopts an Open Science approach. Research findings and data will be available under liberal licences (by default, CC-BY-NC), which allow the redistribution and transformation of the materials for non-commercial purposes.

Resources and cost

Both CSIC and the University of Vigo have open access agreements with the main scientific publishers, including IEEE, ACS, ACM, Oxford University Press, Springer-Nature, Elsevier, and Wiley. These agreements are expected to cover part (or all, in certain cases) of the open access fees for the project's publications.

Furthermore, free repositories such as Github and Zenodo will be used for sharing software and datasets, as already mentioned. Therefore, the estimated cost of data management is low.

Data security

The open/shared datasets will be securely stored, long term preserved and curated in the Zenodo trusted repository. The data published on the websites will be also securely stored and preserved in the partner's server and storage media. Each partner is responsible for the long term preservation and curation of his own test and simulation data. The suggested policy is to use a cloud storage service from our institutions (e.g., saco.csic.es) and create a second backup of all data in external storage devices (NAS or external drives).

Ethics

DYNAMO-bio will not work with personal data (information about an identified or identifiable natural person), nor with any other types of confidential or classified data or code.

There are no ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing and long-term preservation.